

Investigating the Use of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for Pansharpening Thermal Satellite Imagery

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1. Abstract

Remotely sensed satellite imagery can be an important data source for observing and measuring environmental changes in urban areas. For example, thermal satellite imagery can be used to identify urban heat islands (UHIs) and provide motivation for urban cooling strategies. However, the spatial resolution of thermal satellite imagery is insufficient for many urban biodiversity applications (e.g., tree planting and shifting ranges of flora and fauna in response to climate change) because of the inherent heterogeneity and complexity of cities. In order to improve the usability of this imagery, artificial intelligence techniques can increase the spatial resolution of the thermal imagery without losing valuable spectral information. One such technique is pansharpening, which fuses high-spatial resolution panchromatic (single band gray-scale) images and lower-spatial resolution multispectral or thermal infrared images. This project uses a modified generative adversarial network (GAN) to pansharpen lower resolution, remotely sensed thermal satellite imagery using high spatial resolution red-green-blue (RGB) imagery. A focus on developing higher spatial resolution maps of heat across cities could enable such broader-scale investigations into the impacts of UHIs on biodiversity.

This thesis develops a novel training dataset with patch-pairs of co-located thermal (70 m) and RGB imagery (3 m). Using this novel dataset, this thesis assesses whether a pansharpening model (PanColorGAN) trained on RGB and panchromatic imagery can be successfully applied to the thermal-optical patch-pairs to solve the thermal pansharpening problem. In addition, this thesis will determine if a pansharpening model (*pix2pix*) trained on the thermal-optical patch-pairs produces higher quality results than the model with pre-trained weights (PanColorGAN). This approach will be applied to five cities with variable climate-urban environments across the United States: Austin, TX, Boulder, CO, Chicago, IL, Los Angeles, CA, and Washington, D.C. The visual and quantitative results indicated that the PanColorGAN framework with pre-trained weights produced higher quality thermal images than the *pix2pix* framework trained on the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset. While thermal-optical pansharpening successfully recovered many of the spatial details of the high-resolution RGB imagery, it failed to fully retain the valuable spectral information from the thermal imagery.

2. Introduction

2.1. Influence of the urban heat island (UHI) effect

A major trend in human habitation is the movement towards cities, with 54% of the global population now living in cities compared to 30% in 1950. These trends are almost certain to continue, with 67% of the world's population projected to live in cities by 2050. Within the United States, urban areas grew over 10% from 57.9 million acres in 2000 to 68 million acres in 2010 ("World Migration Report 2015" 2015). The process of urbanization has many important implications for social, economic, environmental, and ecological trends (Singh, Singh, and Mall 2020). One reason for this is the urban heat island (UHI) phenomenon, which occurs when urban

areas tend to be warmer than the surrounding suburban and rural areas (Heaviside, Macintyre, and Vardoulakis 2017; Johnson et al. 2019). The development of UHIs is influenced by a combination of uncontrollable factors (e.g., meteorological and diurnal conditions) and controllable factors (e.g., urban design, anthropogenic air pollution, green space, etc.) (Memon, Leung, and Chunho 2008).

Although the negative impacts that UHIs have on human health (e.g., increased risk of hospitalization/death and heat stroke exacerbating pre-existing medical conditions (Heaviside, Macintyre, and Vardoulakis 2017)) are relatively well-understood, there is a lack of research into the ecological impacts of UHIs and the extent of these impacts is not fully understood (Zipper et al. 2016). Areas of urban vegetation and urban biodiversity hotspots can provide essential ecosystem services, such as noise reduction, improved urban air quality, rainwater drainage, and recreational spaces (Bolund and Hunhammar 1999). However, it is possible that the UHI effect may negate the positive effects of ecosystem services and influence the biodiversity trends in urban areas. As such, more detailed studies of how UHIs may be impacting urban ecosystems and biodiversity across a wider range of urban areas would be valuable in elucidating possible trends.

The trend of increasing urban heat caused by the UHI effect is likely to influence the range and ability to thrive of many species of flora and fauna (Wilby and Perry 2006). However, many studies on this topic have been extremely localized (i.e., focusing on specific species or a single urban area) and may not transfer to other cities. One study investigated how UHIs impact moss gardens in Kyoto, Japan and determined that microclimates triggered by the UHI effect strongly affected the type of moss that will grow best (Yoshitaka Oishi 2019). Another study found that UHIs can slow the development of Western black widow spiders, leading to increased mortality in juvenile spiderlings that causes shifts in foraging and web-building behavior (Johnson et al. 2019), which can ultimately affect insect populations. A study of copper lizards and urban heat trends in Phoenix, Arizona saw that summer lizard activity was severely limited in un-irrigated native desert landscaping, but cooler areas with irrigation or shade trees allowed for continual lizard activity, suggesting that lizards may live in more developed irrigated areas in the future (Ackley et al. 2015). One study predicted how the community composition of bee species in Raleigh, North Carolina would change under UHI warming conditions, as social bees tend to be more heat tolerant than solitary bees (Hamblin et al. 2017). While these studies together demonstrate that UHIs can impact local community composition, they are too small-scale and focused on individual urban areas to draw broader conclusions about how UHIs affect biodiversity.

A 2021 ecosystem health report card developed by researchers at UCLA as part of the Sustainable Los Angeles (LA) Grand Challenge gave Los Angeles County a grade of C for land use/habitat quality, B for biodiversity, C for threats to ecosystem health, and C for community health and wellbeing (Reid-Wainscoat et al. 2021). The focus of the “community health and wellbeing” section was largely on the dangers of UHIs in Los Angeles, as extreme heat is the main cause of weather-related deaths in the U.S. and poses profound threats to natural

ecosystems. While this report was prepared specifically for Los Angeles, many of the main conclusions are relevant to other cities in the U.S., underscoring the importance of developing methodologies for studying the impact of urban heat on urban planning and management that are broadly applicable to a wide range of urban areas. For example, one challenge is disentangling which changes in urban biodiversity are caused by changes in land cover (e.g. increasing impervious surface fraction) versus those caused by increased temperatures due to UHIs (Zipper et al. 2016; McGlynn et al. 2019). A focus on developing higher spatial resolution maps of heat across cities could enable such broader-scale investigations into the impacts of UHIs on biodiversity.

2.2. Remotely sensed imagery for urban areas

Given the large spatial footprint and heterogeneity of urban areas spanning private and public governance, an important data source for observing and quantifying the impacts of climate change in these regions is remotely sensed imagery. Remote sensing can be defined as the science of obtaining information about the Earth from a distance, typically using images from a satellite or airborne platform that measures electromagnetic energy reflected or emitted from Earth's surface. An important type of remote sensing sensor is the passive sensor, which measures energy from Earth's surface (as opposed to actively testing how energy from the sensor reacts with the Earth's surface) and works best during daylight and non-cloudy conditions. Two important types of passively sensed imagery are optical and thermal imagery.

Thermal satellite imagery is important for understanding when and where UHIs form, by measuring the land surface temperature and quantifying vegetative water stress (G. Hulley et al. 2019; Zoran et al. 2013). The highest spatial resolution of publicly available thermal satellite imagery has a native spatial resolution of 70×70 m at nadir, but it degrades to 100×100 m at the edge of the swath due to variable view angles (G. C. Hulley et al. 2021). Although this spatial scale is typically sufficient for analysis of non-urban agricultural or forested regions, it is too coarse to pick up fine-scale features in heterogeneous urban environments that are especially relevant for the scale of management (e.g., tree planting). One potential solution to improve the spatial resolution of imagery is superresolution, which is the process of obtaining a high-resolution image from a lower resolution image using traditional mathematical approaches or newer deep learning techniques (Salgueiro Romero, Marcello, and Vilaplana 2020). Most recent advances in remote sensing superresolution have utilized deep learning techniques, which have proven to be extremely valuable for extracting information from satellite imagery and simulating realistic high-resolution imagery that accurately represents the true content of the image (L. Ma et al. 2019).

While optical imagery measures electromagnetic energy from the Earth's surface in the visible range, thermal imagery passively measures energy in the infrared range of the spectrum, including short-wave infrared (SWIR, $0.9 - 1.7 \mu\text{m}$) and long-wave infrared (LWIR $8 - 14 \mu\text{m}$) wavelengths (Kulkarni and Rege 2020). Passive imaging sensors are often characterized by the number of spectral bands each image contains: panchromatic images have 1 spectral band,

multispectral images have multiple broad bands that span across many wavelengths, and imaging spectroscopy has many narrow spectral bands covering the details of the spectral signature over a given wavelength region (Kulkarni and Rege 2020; Lu et al. 2018).

The two main sources of satellite imagery data come from commercial and government providers and there are important tradeoffs in image quality, cost, temporal, spatial, and spectral resolution between commercial and government-based satellite imagery. One major difference between commercial and government remote sensing satellites is spatial resolution. In the optical domain, commercial satellites typically have a spatial resolution less than 5 m, whereas government satellites tend to have spatial resolutions in the range of 10-500 m. Nearly all thermal satellite imagery is from government satellites; there are a limited number of commercial satellite providers in the early stages of developing thermal imaging satellites (e.g., Satellite Vu). Image quality is also an important consideration, as government imagery has more transparent quality assurance methods, is more consistently calibrated, and generally has a higher signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) than commercial imagery. A low SNR value means that the signal that the satellite sensor receives may be corrupted with noise, making it more difficult to recover high-resolution images (Qian 2013). In some cases, commercial satellite imagery can be available at a more frequent temporal cadence, at a higher cost than government imagery, because commercial providers often use a constellation of imaging satellites. Combining commercial and open-source government satellite imagery via data fusion is a promising approach to take advantage of the benefits of both imagery sources (i.e., high spatial and temporal resolution).

2.3. Introduction to generative adversarial networks (GANs) and their application to remotely-sensed imagery

The basic framework of a generative adversarial network (GAN) is that there are two simultaneously trained models; one generative model that captures the data distribution and a separate discriminative model that aims to determine whether the sample came from the training data or from the generative model. This process can be represented by a zero-sum two-player game, where both models are pitted against each other in an adversarial process. Loss functions for each model produce a value that scores the quality of the results produced by a GAN, and minimizing the loss function drives a GAN to produce more realistic results (Isola et al. 2018). The seminal paper on GANs included an excellent analogy to explain how they work at a very fundamental level: “the generative model can be thought of as analogous to a team of counterfeiters, trying to produce fake currency and use it without detection, while the discriminative model is analogous to the police, trying to detect counterfeit currency. Competition in this game drives both teams to improve their methods until the counterfeits are indistinguishable from the genuine articles” (Goodfellow et al. 2014). When GANs are applied to imagery, the generative model attempts to generate images that are so realistic that the discriminator is unable to distinguish between legitimate and faked images (Isola et al. 2018).

An important application of GANs is image fusion, which aims to combine two or more images into a single image that is more informative than each individual image (Fuentes Reyes et al. 2019). One type of image fusion is pansharpening, which is the process of obtaining high-resolution multispectral images by fusing high-resolution panchromatic images and low-resolution multispectral (RGB) images (J. Ma et al. 2020). Pansharpening aims to generate a synthetic high-resolution multispectral image from the low-resolution multispectral image that is a plausible reconstruction of the high-resolution panchromatic image with the addition of multispectral features (**Figure 1**, Ledig et al. 2017).

Figure 1: An example GAN architecture for pansharpening lower spatial resolution multispectral (RGB) imagery and higher spatial resolution panchromatic imagery to create synthetic higher spatial resolution multispectral imagery.

While prior pansharpening papers have focused on sharpening multispectral optical imagery, there is only one published study focused on pansharpening thermal imagery (Raimundo et al. 2021). In this study, Raimundo et al. (2021) showed that multiple pansharpening algorithms applied to simultaneously captured thermal and high-resolution panchromatic drone imagery can be used to generate pansharpened, high-resolution thermal imagery. Importantly, all of the selected methods from this paper were traditional pansharpening approaches and did not rely on deep learning techniques, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) or GANs. While simultaneously acquired imagery is ideal for pansharpening because it minimizes the potential for phenological or physical variation over time, its existence is an unrealistic assumption as this is rarely the case when multiple imagery types are acquired from different satellite platforms, such as optical and thermal imagery.

2.4. Developing a satellite imagery pansharpening training data set

One of the major challenges for applying GANs to novel problems is that they require huge amounts of training data (Tanaka and Aranha 2019). Many published remote sensing

superresolution studies develop a low-resolution training data set with simple down-sampling of the original high-resolution image (e.g., bicubic interpolation). For example, Edge-Enhanced GAN for Remote Sensing (EEGAN) and Enlighten-GAN both performed synthetic downscaling prior to model training in order to create a low-resolution training data set (Gong et al. 2021; Jiang et al. 2019). This approach is effective for testing superresolution with synthetic imagery, but it does not generalize well to actual satellite images, which have different noise signals than standard downsampling and may contain motion blur artifacts (Zhu et al. 2020).

It is challenging to collect high quality, meaningful training data for remote sensing-based models because there is a lot of prerequisite domain knowledge necessary to collect data across the range of variability observed in an image with thousands if not millions or billions of data points (L. Ma et al. 2019). One pre-existing dataset of remotely sensed imagery is the SEN1-2 data set, which contains 282,384 “patch-pairs” of spatiotemporally co-located Sentinel-1 (radar imagery) and Sentinel-2 (optical imagery) image patches to support novel deep learning approaches, including image-to-image translation between synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and optical imagery (Schmitt, Hughes, and Zhu 2018). An artificial bias was introduced into the data set to ensure that enough patch-pairs were collected over urban areas by sampling 100 areas over the entire Earth and 50 urban-only areas. In this thesis, the “patch-pair” approach to generating a training data set of matched images will be extended to other satellite data sources: thermal and optical imagery.

2.5. Project summary

This thesis project assesses the feasibility of generating high spatial resolution thermal imagery from a lower resolution starting point. More specifically, this project pansharpens thermal remotely-sensed imagery with GANs, improving the spatial resolution of the imagery from 70 m to 3 m using novel machine learning techniques (**Figure 2**). This will involve developing a novel training dataset with patch-pairs of co-located thermal (70 m) and RGB imagery (3 m). Using this novel dataset, this thesis will assess whether a pansharpening model (PanColorGAN) trained on RGB and panchromatic imagery can be successfully applied to the thermal-optical patch-pairs to solve the thermal pansharpening problem. In addition, this thesis will determine if a pansharpening model (pix2pix) trained on the thermal-optical patch-pairs produces higher quality results than the model with pre-trained weights (PanColorGAN). Using two disparate GAN model architectures (pix2pix and PanColorGAN) allows comparison of different training strategies and different model architectures to explore different approaches for pansharpening thermal imagery using a GAN. Lastly, both pansharpening approaches will be validated using image quality metrics to assess the resulting sharpened thermal imagery.

Figure 2: An example GAN architecture for pansharpening lower spatial resolution thermal imagery and higher spatial resolution RGB imagery to create synthetic higher spatial resolution thermal imagery.

3. Materials and Methods

Pre-existing pansharpening algorithms revolve around fusing together RGB and panchromatic imagery to synthesize a high spatial resolution multispectral problem. To my knowledge, all published datasets of remotely sensed imagery for pansharpening are patch-pairs of RGB and panchromatic imagery. As such, it was necessary to develop a novel training dataset of thermal-optical patch-pairs for this thesis, which will be addressed in Section 3.1. Section 3.2 will introduce the two GAN frameworks used in this thesis: PanColorGAN to assess if a pansharpening model trained on RGB and panchromatic imagery can be successfully applied to the thermal-optical patch-pairs. *Pix2pix* was used to determine if a pansharpening model trained on the thermal-optical patch-pairs produced higher quality results than PanColorGAN with pre-trained weights. Section 3.3 covers the post-processing steps after pansharpening algorithms have been applied. Section 3.4 introduces the image quality metrics used to assess the spectral and quality of the pansharpened images.

3.1. Developing a training and validation dataset

This thesis adapts the methodology described in Schmitt, Hughes, and Zhu (2018) for creating a thermal-optical patch-pair dataset to work with PlanetScope and ECOSystem Spaceborne Thermal Radiometer Experiment on Space Station (ECOSTRESS) imagery. The training data set will contain co-located pairs of low-resolution thermal images (ECOSTRESS) and high-resolution optical RGB imagery (PlanetScope). The high spatial resolution (3 m) and near-daily acquisitions of PlanetScope imagery make it an ideal data source for generating a large library of thermal-optical patch-pairs. Each patch-pair consists of a 128 x 128 pixel RGB image and a 128 x 128 pixel LST image taken at the same geographic location and within at least

2-3 weeks of each other in order to reduce the potential for land cover or plant physiology change in the imagery.

3.1.1. Selecting target cities

In order to develop a pansharpening methodology that can be generalizable to cities with varied urban environments, rather than a model that is overfitted or specific to a single city, training data was obtained from five different cities. The thermal-optical patch pair library is geographically constrained to the target urban areas of Los Angeles, Austin, Boulder, Chicago, and Washington, D.C. (**Table 1**). These cities were selected to represent a range of urban environmental types, including cities with differing population densities, Köppen climate classifications (Peel, Finlayson, and McMahon 2007), and urban-suburban dynamics.

Table 1: The target urban areas for thermal-optical pansharpening have varied population densities, climate classifications, and area.

City	Population Density (persons/mi ²)	Köppen climate	Land area (mi ²)
Los Angeles, CA	8,484	Hot-summer Mediterranean	503
Austin, TX	3,182	Humid subtropical	272
Chicago, IL	11,883	Humid continental	234
Washington, D.C.	11,158	Humid subtropical	61
Boulder, CO	3,981	Subtropical steppe	27

3.1.2. Introducing ECOSTRESS and Planet Imagery

ECOSTRESS has been actively collecting data since July 2018, measuring thermal infrared (TIR) radiation in five bands spanning the 8 to 12.5 μm wavelength range (Fisher et al. 2020). Because ECOSTRESS is installed on the International Space Station, it has a precessing orbit that leads to sporadic spatial and temporal sampling with revisit frequencies of between 3–5 days depending on latitude and acquisition at varying times of the day. ECOSTRESS pixels have a spatial resolution of 70×70 m at nadir. The focus of this thesis will be the Level-2 LST product, which has an accuracy of 1.07 K over vegetation, water, and soils when compared to ground-based measurements (G. C. Hulley et al. 2021). Although ECOSTRESS is capable of image acquisition over a large portion of the globe, typical downlinked data coverage from the ISS is limited to the continental United States (CONUS).

PlanetScope is a constellation of ~130 earth-observing satellites operated by Planet that covers the entire Earth every day with 3 m spatial resolution RGB-NIR imagery (Planet Team 2017). All PlanetScope imagery undergoes sensor and radiometric calibration prior to publication, including flat-field correction, orthorectification, and surface reflectance processing to remove atmospheric effects. Importantly, the most recent PlanetScope satellites (SuperDoves) are calibrated with Sentinel-2 optical imagery bands and have fewer image quality issues than earlier Planet satellites, so SuperDove imagery was used for this thesis. As a member of the Planet Education & Research program, I was able to download up to 5,000 square kilometers of PlanetScope imagery per month via Planet’s API, which was sufficient to develop a library of 6,788 thermal-optical patch-pairs. The Education & Research program is available to any university-affiliated students, faculty members, or researchers, as well as other researchers at non-profits or government institutions.

3.1.3. Co-locating ECOSTRESS and Planet Imaging

For each of the five target cities, a shapefile representing the bounding box of the urban area was acquired through an online open-source data portal (“County of Los Angeles Enterprise Geographic Information” n.d.; “TxDOT Open Data Portal” n.d.; “City of Chicago Data Portal” n.d.; “Open Data DC” n.d.; “Open Data Boulder” n.d.). Twenty-five random points were selected in each target city and a 2 km square buffer was generated around each randomly selected point to create a region of interest (ROI) using the randomPoints() function in Google Earth Engine. Any ROI that overlapped with a previously generated ROI was removed, as were any ROIs that were more than 50% outside of the study area. All remaining ROIs were then exported from Google Earth Engine (GEE) as a shapefile. This process resulted in 10 ROIs in Washington, D.C., 20 ROIs in Chicago, 20 ROIs in Los Angeles, 20 ROIs in Austin, and 9 ROIs in Boulder (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Distribution of ROIs in target cities, where each ROI has an area of 2 km². (a) 20 ROIs in Austin, (b) 20 ROIs in Chicago, (c) 20 ROIs in Los Angeles, (d) 9 ROIs in Boulder, (e) 10 ROIs in Washington, D.C.

In order to generate a training dataset that accounts for the effects of seasonality, ECOSTRESS and Planet imagery from each ROI during all four seasons of 2020 was used. The seasons of 2020 are defined as winter (December, January, February), spring (March, April, May), summer (June, July, August), and fall (September, October, November). Given the longer revisit period for ECOSTRESS compared to daily PlanetScope coverage, ECOSTRESS imagery was the limiting factor for finding co-located thermal-optical image pairs that had been acquired within the same month to minimize the potential for phenological or land cover change in the imagery. Day-time ECOSTRESS imagery with minimal to no cloud cover that overlapped with each target city's ROIs was downloaded using NASA's EarthData Search platform. This required downloading both the ECOSTRESS Land Surface Temperature (LST) and Emissivity Daily L2 Global 70m V001 and Geolocation Daily L1B Global 70m V001 to run the ECOSTRESS swath2grid.py function, which converts the downloaded ECOSTRESS swath data products (stored in .h5 files) to projected GeoTIFF files (stored in .tif files) using nearest neighbor resampling (Krehbiel, Cole 2021).

After ECOSTRESS imagery dates for each season and target city were identified, tiles of cloud-free 4-band imagery from Planet's SuperDove satellites captured within a month of each desired ECOSTRESS acquisition were downloaded using Planet's online API ("Planet Explorer" n.d.). Planet imagery tiles (25 x 25 km) have a substantially smaller swath width than ECOSTRESS imagery tiles (384 x 384 km), so it was necessary to merge together multiple Planet tiles for each target city and season to cover the entire study area. Seasonal Planet and ECOSTRESS data were then clipped to the ROIs for each target city and reprojected to the same coordinate reference system (EPSG 4326). Each 2 km ROI was split into non-overlapping 128 x 128 pixel patches, then each pixel patch was saved as a unique, georeferenced .tif file (**Figure 4**). Any leftover portions of the 2 km ROI after tiling that were smaller than 128 x 128 pixels were not included in the training data set. The 128 x 128 pixel patch size is based on the RGB imagery, so this means that each pixel is assumed to be 3 m in spatial resolution. This means that the number of RGB pixels in a 128 x 128 patch is 16,384 PlanetScope 3 m² pixels and that the number of LST pixels in a 128 x 128 patch is ~30 ECOSTRESS 70 m² pixels.

Figure 4: Based on the tiling procedure for this dataset, each pixel is assumed to be 3 m in spatial resolution. (a) 3 m RGB imagery is overlaid with 128 x 128 pixel patches in red, (b) 70 m LST imagery is overlaid with 128 x 128 pixel patches in red.

3.1.4. Manual inspection for corrupted/edge tiles

After image tiling was complete, all patch-pairs were manually inspected to ensure that they did not contain corrupted LST or RGB imagery, leading to a final patch-pair count of 8,410. After removing any corrupted patch-pairs, 2,002 were from Austin, 714 were from Boulder, 1,099 were from Washington, D.C., 2,102 were from Los Angeles, and 2,493 were from Chicago. Each patch-pair has a unique image ID that indicates the city, original ROI, and tile identity within the ROI. For example, given the patch-pair “0_austin_fall_1_5,” it is known that this patch-pair is from Austin, the ROI is from the Austin ROI shapefile with filename FID_0.shp, and it is the unique tile located at row 1, column 5 within the FID_0 ROI after tiling is complete.

Examples of image corruption include cloud cover, snow cover, or obvious imaging sensor malfunctions (**Figure 5, a and b**). In Austin, Washington, D.C., Los Angeles, and Chicago, it was possible to select winter imagery that did not have substantial snowfall. However, in Boulder, all image patch-pairs during the winter season were removed from the training data set due to persistent snow cover that could interfere with the pansharpening algorithm due to differences in the thermal-optical imagery relationship. Additionally, any patch-pairs that fell on the edge of the target city shapefile (**Figure 5, c**) were flagged and a metadata field was added that identified whether a patch-pair was an “edge” or “non-edge” patch.

Figure 5: (a) A snow-corrupted 128 x 128 patch-pair from Boulder, (b) A cloud-corrupted 128 x 128 patch-pair from Chicago, (c) An “edge” 128 x 128 patch-pair from Chicago

3.1.5. Patch-pair assessment with NLCD data

To investigate applicability of higher-resolution thermal imagery from pansharpening for broader changes in biodiversity due to increased urban temperatures, it was important to ensure that the patch-pair training data set is balanced across landcover classes. One potential concern was that the randomly selected ROIs, and in turn, the image patch-pairs, might not be evenly distributed across the urban areas. This could potentially lead to a clustering of data points in one geographic area or a data set that was skewed towards certain landcover classes. This could make it difficult to develop a GAN model that is transferable across urban areas and representative of a variety of landcover classes.

In order to determine how representative the randomly selected ROIs were of multiple landcover classes within each target city, the landcover class fraction of each ROI was calculated and aggregated. A widely used, open-source landcover dataset that is available across CONUS is the National Land Cover Database (NLCD), which is developed by the USGS every two to three years at 30 m spatial resolution using Landsat imagery (Jin et al. 2019). The 2016 NLCD dataset was used for this assessment because it is respected as one of the definitive landcover classifications with over 20 distinct landcover classes and an 82% accuracy for the 2016 dataset (**Figure 6**). Given the large number of landcover classes in the NLCD dataset and the relatively small fraction of non-developed landcover pixels in most urban areas, the NLCD classes were binned into the broader landcover groups of Developed, Forest, Grassland/Scrub, Wetlands, and Water/Barren Land. As expected, over 50% of the ROI area in all target cities was some form of developed landcover (**Figure 7a**). The per-city distributions of the ROIs corresponded with the expected landcover fraction from the whole city, suggesting that this data set was generally balanced between landcover types (**Figure 7b**).

Figure 6: (a) All 9 ROIs in Boulder showing NLCD 2016 data, (b) Closer view of NLCD 2016 data in one randomly selected Boulder ROI, (c) Google Earth base imagery of the same randomly selected Boulder ROI.

Figure 7: (a) Distribution of 2016 NLCD landcover classes binned into categories of landcover type across the entire bounding box of each target city, (b) Distribution of 2016 NLCD landcover classes binned into categories of landcover type within the ROIs of each target city.

3.1.6. Patch-pair preprocessing

Prior to training and testing different GAN-based pansharpener models, it was necessary to preprocess the patch-pairs by splitting between training and test data, then normalizing the imagery, and performing data augmentation. Following the common machine learning procedure of splitting a data set into training data and test data, 70% of patch-pairs (5,923) were randomly assigned to be training patch-pairs and 30% (2,487) were assigned to be testing patch-pairs. The

70/30 split between testing and training data was not explicitly balanced across cities. Training data was used for training all GAN models, whereas testing data was left untouched during training and only used after GAN training was complete to assess how well the GAN performed on unseen training data.

In order to prepare patch-pairs for GAN training, the thermal and RGB values of each patch-pair needed to be normalized between -1 and 1, as this is standard practice to ensure that all data inputs are on a common scale. Normalization was especially important for the thermal-optical patch-pairs because Planet imagery and ECOSTRESS imagery do not have values with the same units. Rather, ECOSTRESS LST imagery has units of Kelvin, while Planet RGB imagery has units of nm, representing the different spectral bands. While both ECOSTRESS and Planet imagery were originally downloaded as GeoTiff files, it was necessary to convert them to JPEG imagery so that they were compatible with existing GAN architectures in Google Colab. This required normalizing Planet and LST imagery from 0-255, as this is the standard range for exporting images as JPEG files. For the Planet imagery, normalization from 0-255 had minimal impact on the information stored in the RGB image because 0-255 is how RGB images are commonly represented. However, for the ECOSTRESS imagery, each LST patch had to be normalized between 0-255 individually, with the local minimum and local maximum values of LST within the patch saved in a lookup table for denormalization after pansharpening.

An alternative approach to LST normalization would have been to globally normalize all LST images using the same global minimum and maximum LST values. For the entire thermal-optical patch-pair dataset, the global minimum/maximum LST values were 271 and 325 K (28 and 125 °F), respectively. However, global normalization was not feasible for this thesis. When local normalization is applied, the LST values in an image are converted to a range of integer values 0-255. However, when global normalization is applied, the range of LST values in an individual image is much smaller (e.g., 25-28), because the global minimum/maximum LST values are not found in every image. Given the integer (discrete) range of normalized values in the globally normalized image that can map to the original LST values, not enough information is maintained to capture thermal variation across the range of all possible (continuous) LST values needed to correctly denormalize the pansharpened image. As such, performing local normalization from Kelvin to 0-255 was necessary for the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset.

Prior to GAN training, both the Planet and ECOSTRESS images of each patch-pair were independently normalized between -1 and 1 using:

$$x' = 2 \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} - 1 \quad \text{(Equation 1)}$$

The minimum and maximum LST and RGB values for each patch-pair were saved in a look-up table so that the values could be later used for denormalization of the pansharpened LST image back to Kelvin using:

$$x = \min(x) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\max(x) - \min(x)}{x' + 1} \quad \text{(Equation 2)}$$

3.2. Training approaches for *pix2pix* and *PanColorGAN* architectures

This thesis project tested the applicability of two GAN-based pansharpening algorithms to the problem of pansharpening thermal imagery: *pix2pix* and *PanColorGAN* (**Figure 8**). The *pix2pix* framework was used to test the feasibility of training a new GAN model for pansharpening with the thermal-optical patch-pairs. The *PanColorGAN* framework was used to test the applicability of a pre-trained GAN model for traditional RGB-panchromatic pansharpening to thermal-optical pansharpening. The expected end product of both the modified *PanColorGAN* and *pix2pix* architectures is a pansharpened thermal image, given an input thermal-optical patch-pair. All GAN implementation and training was performed in Google Colab Pro, which is a product from Google Research that enables writing and executing Python 3 code in a browser and provides access to a graphical processing unit (GPU) for faster execution.

The *pix2pix* architecture is a generic image-to-image translation framework that is easily adaptable to new datasets, making it a good choice for training and testing a GAN model developed only using the thermal-optical patch-pairs. Given the limited size of the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset (8,410 patch-pairs) and challenges of developing large, high-quality remotely sensed datasets for machine learning, this thesis project aimed to assess the feasibility of transferring a pre-trained GAN model to the novel problem of thermal pansharpening. *PanColorGAN* was designed specifically for panchromatic and multispectral satellite imagery, suggesting that it would be able to translate to the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset without additional model training. Lastly, the *pix2pix* algorithm is well-documented on Google Colab and is relatively simple to adapt to novel datasets, while the *PanColorGAN* training code was more complex and adapting it to a novel thermal-optical patch-pair dataset was outside the scope of this thesis project.

Figure 8: Methodology flowchart for applying the two GAN architectures (in yellow) to pansharpen the thermal-optical patch-pairs. (a) *Pix2pix* was trained on and applied to the thermal-optical patch-pairs, (b) PanColorGAN was applied to the thermal-optical patch-pairs using pre-trained weights from an independent remote sensing dataset.

3.2.1. *Pix2Pix*

Pix2pix is an image-to-image translation algorithm, which means that it learns the mapping from an input image in one domain to an output image in another domain (Isola et al. 2018). For example, image-to-image translation could be used to convert from black and white to color imagery, from a segmented image to a realistic image, or from a daytime to a nighttime image. Traditional algorithms for image-to-image translation are very application-specific, making it difficult to replicate the same approach on a different problem. The *pix2pix* algorithm changed this paradigm by using a standard conditional GAN architecture that can be generalized to many disparate image-to-image translation problems (Isola et al. 2018). Image-to-image translation GAN architectures, like *pix2pix*, have been modified to work more effectively with remotely sensed imagery. For example, these novel GAN architectures have been used to generate a cloud-corrected optical image, given an input cloud-corrupted optical image and an auxiliary SAR image from the SEN1-2 dataset (Grohnfeldt, Schmitt, and Zhu 2018) and to translate a basemap of a city to a new satellite image that has the landscape and design of another city (Zhao et al. 2021).

Although the *pix2pix* algorithm was not originally applied to pansharpening, pansharpening can be considered as an image-to-image translation problem, where a high spatial resolution panchromatic image is translated into a high spatial resolution multispectral image.

Adapting this paradigm to the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset, the high spatial resolution multispectral image will be translated into a high spatial resolution thermal image. The *pix2pix* algorithm is well documented on Google Colab and is relatively simple to adapt to novel data sets, so the code was modified to work with the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset, rather than the original input dataset that converted building facade outlines to synthetic building facade images (*Pix2pix.Ipynb* 2019). The *pix2pix* model was left to train using the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset for 30,000 epochs (23.35 minutes with Google Colab, 12.38 minutes with Google Colab Pro), and then image quality metrics were calculated on a subset of the translated test images.

The standard implementation details for *pix2pix* are based on the published tutorial on Google Colab. For the *pix2pix* model, the generator is a modified U-net with a decoder-encoder up-sampler and down-sampler with skip connections connecting all layers together. The discriminator used was a convolutional PatchGAN classifier, which operates by determining how realistic individual image patches seem. Both the generator loss and discriminator loss functions used sigmoid cross-entropy loss, and they both used Adam optimizers.

Similar to most other machine learning models, GANs can produce more accurate and realistic results when provided with more training data. However, constructing remote sensing datasets for machine learning is time consuming due to prerequisite domain knowledge needed to identify training samples (e.g., different landcover classes) and to manually inspect for corrupt images. One way to synthesize additional training samples is via data augmentation, which can increase the number of training samples by slightly modifying existing data (e.g., rotating, mirroring, and adding jitter to patch-pairs). Data augmentation is especially important for this thesis because of the relatively small number of patch-pairs (8,410), compared to previously published datasets like SEN1-2, which consisted of 282,384 patch-pairs across the globe (Schmitt, Hughes, and Zhu 2018). Prior to training the *pix2pix* network with thermal-optical patch-pairs, data augmentation techniques of jitter, rotation, and horizontal/vertical mirroring were applied to each patch-pair in order to double the number of training samples (**Figure 9**).

Figure 9: Example of augmented RGB patch-pair imagery, where an original 128 x 128 patch-pair has been mirrored, rotated, and jittered to increase the number of training patches. For each patch-pair, the same transformation is applied to the corresponding thermal imagery (not pictured).

3.2.2. *PanColorGAN*

In order to assess how well a traditional RGB/panchromatic pansharpening model could be transferred to the novel thermal-optical pansharpening problem, a model with pretrained weights from the original PanColorGAN was applied to the thermal-optical patch-pairs. The PanColorGAN network architecture treats pansharpening as a colorization problem, rather than traditional pansharpening methods that aim to generate a high resolution version of a multispectral image (Ozcelik et al. 2021). One motivation for this change is that using a GAN-based colorization approach helps to avoid spatial detail loss and blurring that frequently occurs with traditional pansharpening algorithms. The PanColorGAN model and interactive Google Colab script are published on GitHub with the pretrained weights (Ozcelik 2022), so the code was modified to work with the thermal-optical data set. PanColorGAN uses a relativistic average GAN (RaGAN) framework, which estimates the probability that real imagery is more realistic than fake imagery, rather than the traditional GAN generator that estimates the probability that fake data is real (Jolicoeur-Martineau 2018). Like *pix2pix*, the RaGAN discriminator uses a PatchGAN classifier. The PanColorGAN model uses mean absolute error (MAE, L1) loss for the reconstruction loss and a specific RaGAN loss for the adversarial generator and discriminator loss functions. Importantly, PanColorGAN was developed for panchromatic and multispectral satellite imagery, suggesting that it may translate better to the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset than the original *pix2pix* model, which was developed for more general image types.

3.3. *Gaussian smoothing to reduce edge effects*

The pansharpened images produced by the pre-trained PanColorGAN framework had a propensity for edge effects along the borders of the 70 m LST pixels. This is not entirely surprising, given that the temperature between subsequent LST pixels is likely to vary and can lead to spectral differences between neighboring 70 m LST pixels. However, edge effects are not desirable in pansharpened imagery because it makes the image less representative of the ground-truth spatial qualities. One method for minimizing image noise like edge effects is Gaussian smoothing (Charalampidis 2009; Janecki 2012). Gaussian filters can reduce image noise and give the appearance of a “smoother” image by giving less weight to pixels located further away from the kernel center. This is particularly valuable for smoothing edge effects because the pixels furthest from the kernel center are those that contain edge artifacts.

The blur quality of a Gaussian filter depends on the sigma value, or the standard deviation, for the Gaussian kernel. Higher values of sigma correspond to a stronger blur effect, while a sigma of 0 means that no blurring is applied. Images with a stronger Gaussian blur will lose some spatial resolution as it gets smoothed out, but these images will also have fewer edge effects. One challenge of Gaussian smoothing is determining the most appropriate sigma value that minimizes the visual appearance of edge effects while maintaining the improved spatial resolution of the sharpened image. In order to determine the most appropriate sigma value for the

pansharpening problem, a subset of training images were sharpened using the PanColorGAN framework, and then smoothed with varied sigma values ($\sigma = 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$).

3.4. Image quality metrics

When considering the quality and accuracy of pansharpened thermal imagery, it is important to quantify the extent to which the thermal (spectral) and spatial content have been retained in the synthesized high-resolution imagery. Most published papers on pansharpening begin with high-resolution RGB imagery, artificially downsample it to create a low-resolution RGB image, and then attempt to recreate a realistic high-resolution RGB image by pansharpening the artificial low-resolution RGB image with a high-resolution panchromatic image (J. Ma et al. 2020; Liu et al. 2020). This is ideal for validation because it allows for direct and quantitative comparison between the original high-resolution RGB image and the pansharpened RGB image. Unfortunately, high-resolution training datasets are not always available, particularly when working with real-world, satellite imagery. In addition, low-resolution satellite imagery has different types of noise and spectral distortion that are not captured by artificial downsampling, making this validation approach less relevant. There are no publicly available datasets of remotely sensed thermal imagery with a spatial resolution higher than that of ECOSTRESS (70 m), so this thesis lacks a high-resolution, ground-truth thermal dataset. In order to get around this issue, alternative methods of assessing the quality of pansharpened thermal imagery were used.

Assessing the quality of pansharpened satellite imagery is an open area of research. Multiple metrics have been proposed to quantitatively evaluate the final output image from different pansharpening GAN methodologies. For instance, Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) is used for understanding the spectral and spatial distortion of a sharpened image (Raimundo et al. 2021). Erreur Relative Global Adimensionnelle de Synthèse (ERGAS) is a statistic that expresses the quality of a sharpened image and considers both spectral and spatial information (J. Ma et al. 2020). Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM) is a metric that measures the spectral distortion in an image (Salgueiro Romero, Marcello, and Vilaplana 2020). All of these image quality metrics are available as functions in the Python *sewar* package (Khalel 2022).

Each function takes in a “ground-truth” spectral or spatial image (i.e., ECOSTRESS LST or PlanetScope RGB imagery) and a pansharpened LST image. RMSE spectral, ERGAS spectral, and SAM compare the pansharpened image to a spectral ground-truth: the corresponding ECOSTRESS LST image. RMSE spatial and ERGAS spatial compare the pansharpened image to a spatial ground-truth: the corresponding PlanetScope RGB image. For both of the pansharpening models used in this thesis (*pix2pix* and PatchColorGAN), RMSE, ERGAS, and SAM were calculated for all normalized pansharpened images. Using this data, a separate histogram distribution of each metric was created for the two pansharpening models used in order to assess how spectral and spatial image quality varied between models. The non-parametric Mann-Whitney U-test was used to test whether two distributions of image quality

metrics (e.g., SAM for *pix2pix* and SAM for PanColorGAN) differed at a statistically significant level.

4. Results

4.1. Comparing GAN architectures

This thesis project tested the applicability of two GAN-based pansharpening algorithms to the problem of pansharpening thermal imagery: *pix2pix* and PanColorGAN. The *pix2pix* framework was used to test the feasibility of training a new GAN model for pansharpening with the thermal-optical patch-pairs. The PanColorGAN framework was used to test the applicability of a pre-trained GAN model for traditional RGB-panchromatic pansharpening to thermal-optical pansharpening. Both the PanColorGAN and *pix2pix* architectures were applied to 2,000 of the “testing” thermal-optical patch-pairs in order to generate synthetic, pansharpened thermal images.

4.1.1. Pix2Pix

The *pix2pix* GAN architecture is an extension of the image-to-image translation problem, but it has not been traditionally applied to pansharpening. The *pix2pix* GAN architecture takes in a lower spatial resolution thermal image (**Figure 10 a**) and a higher spatial resolution RGB image (**Figure 10 b**) to generate a higher spatial resolution thermal image (**Figure 10 d**). Training on the novel thermal-optical patch-pair training dataset for 30,000 epochs starting from a 128 x 128 pixel image of randomly generated noise (**Figure 10 c**), did not adequately maintain the high-resolution spatial features from the RGB image or the spectral features from the corresponding LST image. Instead, pansharpened images appear largely indistinguishable from each other and have repeated grid-like features that are not representative of the high-resolution RGB imagery.

Figure 10: Pansharpening a thermal-optical patch-pair following the *pix2pix* GAN architecture. (a) 128 x 128 ECOSTRESS LST imagery, (b) 128 x 128 PlanetScope RGB imagery, (c) 128 x

128 random noise synthesized by the *pix2pix* generator prior to training, (d) Pansharpended thermal imagery after 30,000 epochs of training.

4.1.2. PanColorGAN

Unlike traditional image-to-image translation approaches (like *pix2pix*) to pansharpending that aim to generate a high resolution version of a multispectral image the PanColorGAN network architecture treats pansharpending as a colorization problem. The PanColorGAN architecture takes in a lower spatial resolution thermal image and a higher spatial resolution RGB image to generate a higher spatial resolution thermal image. Given that this network was already pre-trained with RGB-panchromatic patch-pairs, both training and test thermal-optical patch-pairs were sharpened with PanColorGAN.

In contrast to the *pix2pix* results, the pansharpended images that were synthesized by the PanColorGAN network appeared to maintain many of the high-resolution spatial features from the ground-truth RGB images (**Figure 11 a, c**). However, the resulting pansharpended images also contained edge artifacts along the borders of all LST pixels, which are not representative of spatial features of the ground-truth RGB images. In addition, the pansharpended images did not fully retain the spectral features of the original thermal LST imagery. Instead, the range of values from the pansharpended image (**Figure 11 c**) was generally close to the expected LST values (**Figure 11 b**), but it was much smaller than expected. For example, in the bottom row of **Figure 11**, the expected range of LST values was 298-303 K, but the pansharpended image had a range of 304.07-304.12 K. This suggests that the PanColorGAN pansharpending captured the higher resolution spatial features of the RGB image well, but failed to fully capture the spectral range of the original LST image.

Figure 11: Pansharpending a thermal-optical patch-pair following the PanColorGAN architecture. (a) 128 x 128 PlanetScope RGB imagery, (b) 128 x 128 ECOSTRESS LST imagery [Kelvin], (c) Pansharpended thermal imagery [Kelvin].

4.2. Gaussian smoothing

To correct the edge effects resulting from pansharpening thermal-optical patch-pairs with PanColorGAN, Gaussian smoothing was applied. This minimized the visual appearance of edge effects while maintaining the improved spatial resolution of the sharpened image as much as possible. In order to determine the most appropriate sigma value for the pansharpening problem, a subset of training images were sharpened using the PanColorGAN framework, and then smoothed with varied sigma values (**Figure 12**). Based on a visual assessment of multiple pansharpened and Gaussian smoothed images, $\sigma = 4$ was determined to be the most effective sigma value that removed the strongest edge artifacts while retaining the higher quality spatial features. Thus, Gaussian smoothing with $\sigma = 4$ was included as a post-processing step after pansharpening with PanColorGAN, and was then followed by denormalization back to LST (**Figure 13**).

Figure 12: Visualizing the effect of changing sigma for Gaussian smoothing. (a) No Gaussian smoothing, (b) $\sigma = 2$, (c), $\sigma = 4$, (d) $\sigma = 6$, (e) $\sigma = 8$, (f) $\sigma = 10$.

Figure 13: Pansharpening a thermal-optical patch-pair following the PanColorGAN architecture. (a) 128 x 128 PlanetScope RGB imagery, (b) 128 x 128 ECOSTRESS LST imagery [Kelvin], (c) Pansharpened thermal imagery [Kelvin] (d) Pansharpened thermal imagery with Gaussian smoothing ($\sigma = 4$, [Kelvin]).

4.3. Image quality metrics

In order to quantitatively assess whether *pix2pix* or PanColorGAN produce higher quality pansharpened thermal imagery, three common image quality metrics (RMSE, ERGAS, and SAM) were calculated for 2,000 pansharpened test patch-pairs.

4.3.1. RMSE

RMSE is used to measure either the spatial or spectral distortion of a pansharpened image against the ground-truth RGB or LST imagery, respectively. Higher values of RMSE correspond to increased levels of spatial or spectral distortion. For both PanColorGAN and *pix2pix*, spectral distortion is higher than spatial distortion, which suggests that pansharpening thermal imagery preserves high-resolution spatial features better than the spectral information from the target LST imagery (**Figure 14**). When comparing the distribution of RMSE for PanColorGAN and *pix2pix*, the spectral and spatial RMSE of images sharpened with *pix2pix* is higher than those sharpened with PanColorGAN, which indicates that PanColorGAN produces less distorted pansharpened thermal images. The distributions are significantly different between RMSE spatial and spectral distortion for *pix2pix*, between RMSE spatial and spectral distortion for PanColorGAN, RMSE spatial distortion between *pix2pix* and PanColorGAN, and RMSE spectral distortion between *pix2pix* and PanColorGAN (Mann-Whitney U-test, $p < 0.05$ for all tests).

Figure 14: RMSE measures the spectral or spatial distortion of a pansharpened image. Each distribution of RMSE values represents 2000 pansharpened test images. (a) Spectral distortion of images sharpened with PanColorGAN, (b) Spatial distortion of images sharpened with PanColorGAN, (c) Spectral distortion of images sharpened with *pix2pix*, (d) Spatial distortion of images sharpened with *pix2pix*.

4.3.2. ERGAS

Similar results to RMSE were found for ERGAS, which is used to measure the spatial or spectral quality of a pansharpened image against the ground-truth RGB or LST imagery, respectively. Higher levels of ERGAS correspond to images with lower spatial or spectral quality. For both PanColorGAN and *pix2pix*, spatial quality is higher than spectral quality, which suggests that pansharpening thermal imagery preserves high-resolution spatial features better than the spectral information from the target LST imagery (**Figure 15**). When comparing the distribution of ERGAS for PanColorGAN and *pix2pix*, the spectral and spatial ERGAS of images sharpened with *pix2pix* is higher than those sharpened with PanColorGAN, which indicates that PanColorGAN produces higher quality pansharpened thermal images. The distributions are significantly different between ERGAS spatial and spectral distortion for *pix2pix*, between ERGAS spatial and spectral distortion for PanColorGAN, ERGAS spatial

distortion between *pix2pix* and PanColorGAN, and ERGAS spectral distortion between *pix2pix* and PanColorGAN (Mann-Whitney U-test, $p < 0.05$ for all tests).

Figure 15: ERGAS measures the spectral or spatial quality of a pansharpened image. Each distribution of ERGAS values represents 2000 pansharpened test images. (a) Spectral distortion of images sharpened with PanColorGAN, (b) Spatial distortion of images sharpened with PanColorGAN, (c) Spectral distortion of images sharpened with *pix2pix*, (d) Spatial distortion of images sharpened with *pix2pix*.

4.3.3. SAM

The results of analyzing the distribution of SAM within the 2000 sharpened test images were consistent with the results from ERGAS and RMSE. SAM is used to measure the spatial distortion of a pansharpened image against the ground-truth RGB imagery. Higher values of SAM correspond to increased levels of spatial or spectral distortion. When comparing the distribution of SAM for PanColorGAN and *pix2pix*, the SAM of images sharpened with *pix2pix* is higher and more variable than those sharpened with PanColorGAN, which indicates that PanColorGAN produces less spectrally distorted pansharpened thermal images (**Figure 16**). The distributions are significantly different for SAM spectral distortion between *pix2pix* and PanColorGAN (Mann-Whitney U-test, $p < 0.05$ for all tests).

Figure 16: SAM measures the spectral distortion of a pansharpened image. Each histogram represents 2000 pansharpened test images. (a) Spectral distortion of images sharpened with PanColorGAN, (b) Spectral distortion of images sharpened with *pix2pix*.

5. Discussion

5.1. Is the sharpened product actually “thermal” imagery?

While there are numerous challenges of training GANs with remote sensing data, such as computational and time costs, amount of training data, and a lack of objective metrics for visual quality evaluation, the main issue for this thesis was that the pansharpened “thermal” imagery did not have the correct range of Kelvin to correspond to pure thermal imagery after denormalization. This is also supported by the image quality metric analysis that showed pansharpened images have more spectral distortion than spatial distortion. Interestingly, the issue of incorrect units on the final product while performing image-to-image translation has appeared in a previously published study that looked at methods for converting between SAR and optical satellite imagery. The authors hypothesized that it is not possible to fully convert from SAR to optical imagery or vice versa using GANs, but that the resulting image will be a product that is in between the two data types (Fuentes Reyes et al. 2019).

One reason for this discrepancy in units may be the method by which LST images were normalized during patch-pair creation. Each LST image was normalized locally between 0-255 separately and the local minimum and maximum LST values in that patch-pair were recorded in a lookup table for denormalization after pansharpening. Unfortunately, the applied approach of local normalization meant that normalized temperature values were not directly comparable between patch-pairs. Both the thermal and optical images in the patch-pairs needed to be normalized to integer values between 0-255, so that they could be exported to JPEG files that are compatible with the TensorFlow framework in Google Colab. Ideally, it would have been possible to only normalize both images to continuous values between $[-1, 1]$ prior to pansharpening, and then denormalize back to the original units of nm and K after sharpening, as

this would have maintained the maximum amount of information in the images. As such, future work should focus on developing a pipeline that works with GeoTiff imagery, rather than only JPEG images. This would be valuable to the broader field of remote sensing because many pre-built deep learning architectures for imagery assume that the input is a JPEG, whereas remotely sensed imagery is typically acquired as a georeferenced GeoTiff that allows for a wider range of spectral data.

5.2. Ethics of using GANs for pansharpening thermal imagery

While there are many powerful applications of GANs to satellite imagery, such as reconstructing historical scenes, predicting land cover and land use change, or automatically creating basemaps, there are also important ethical issues to take into consideration when using GAN technology. One of the most well-known applications of GANs are “deep fakes,” which are hyper-realistic, generated images or audio clips that can be extremely challenging to distinguish from real imagery (Westerlund 2019). Deep fake technology can be used to generate pornographic or political videos of an individual saying anything, without the consent of the person whose face and likeness is being used (Verdoliva 2020). GANs are becoming increasingly accessible, as websites and apps are being developed for creating deep fakes with minimal to no coding experience required. Specific to satellite imagery, there are national security risks associated with using GANs, as faked images could be used to convince people that there is a flood or a wildfire, or to mislead other countries with spoofed military sites (Nyberg 2021; Zhao et al. 2021). Importantly, the adversarial nature of GANs means that it can be challenging to detect deep fakes in geospatial data because the generator and adversary are always getting more realistic, making this a serious concern if the technology is misused (Zhao et al. 2021).

Although this thesis project is largely experimental and exploratory, it is still important to consider the ethical implications of pansharpening thermal imagery and performing superresolution with GAN technology. For example, if pansharpened thermal imagery is not properly validated against other reliable data sources and is then used for identifying the location or severity of UHIs, researchers could run the risk of incorrectly predicting where UHIs are most likely to form and lead to important heat-reducing resources being distributed in the wrong communities. More importantly, because there is very little published research on using GANs to sharpen satellite imagery and GAN architecture can be transferred to novel datasets, there is always a chance that this research could fall into the wrong hands and be used maliciously.

5.3. Future work

5.3.1. Increasing size of thermal-optical patch-pair dataset

One potential reason for the non-specific pansharpened images produced by the *pix2pix* model trained with the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset is that the number of patch-pairs was too low to train a high quality GAN pansharpening model. The thermal-optical patch-pair dataset contains 8,410 patch-pairs, but this is substantially fewer training and test images than other

published GAN-based pansharpening algorithms. For example, PSGAN used 50,050 training/test images from QuickBird, WorldView-2, and GaoFen-2 (Liu et al. 2020), while PanColorGAN used 30,000 training and 5,700 test images from the Pleiades satellite constellation (Ozcelik et al. 2021), and Pan-GAN used 50,000 training image patch-pairs from WorldView-2 and GaoFen-2 (J. Ma et al. 2020). GAN models are notorious for requiring large training datasets in order to produce realistic, non-overfitted synthetic images (Zhao et al. 2021), so it is not surprising that the small size of the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset limited the quality of *pix2pix* pansharpened thermal images.

There were several limitations to increasing the size of the thermal-optical patch-pair data set. In order to constrain the scope of this project to a senior thesis that could be completed in one academic year, the number of target cities was limited to five. While these cities were selected to represent a range of urban environmental types, including cities with differing population densities and climate classifications, the area that they cover is insufficient to produce enough unique 128 x 128 pixel patch-pairs. In addition, manual inspection of thermal-optical patch-pairs to ensure that patch-pairs did not contain clouds or other visual aberrations was time consuming. Although the PlanetScope and ECOSTRESS online APIs provided cloud filtering mechanisms, these methods do not catch all clouds, making it necessary to double-check that patch-pairs are not corrupted. Given these limitations, future research should focus on making the methodology developed in this thesis for creating thermal-optical patch-pairs faster and expanding it to other urban areas.

5.3.2. Pan-GAN pansharpening architecture

One GAN pansharpening architecture that looks particularly promising for pansharpening thermal imagery using weights trained on the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset is Pan-GAN. The Pan-GAN novel network architecture was designed specifically for pansharpening remotely sensed imagery and it aims to preserve both the spatial content of panchromatic imagery and the spectral content of RGB imagery (J. Ma et al. 2020). Like *pix2pix*, Pan-GAN is an unsupervised learning method that does not rely on high-resolution ground truth RGB imagery during training. This is highly relevant because such ground truth datasets do not always exist when working with satellite imagery. In contrast to other GAN architectures that have a single generator and a single discriminator, the Pan-GAN architecture contains two independently trained discriminators: one for preserving spectral content and another for preserving spatial content. The original Pan-GAN code was written in Python using TensorFlow and published on GitHub (Yu 2022), but the code will need to be substantially modified to run in Google Colab. Adapting Pan-GAN to the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset would mean that the Pan-GAN architecture will aim to preserve the spatial content of the RGB imagery and the spectral content of the LST imagery, ideally producing a higher quality and more realistic pansharpened thermal image.

5.4. Conclusion

This thesis project aimed to assess the feasibility of generating high spatial resolution thermal imagery from a lower resolution starting point. More specifically, two GAN frameworks (*pix2pix* and PanColorGAN) were used to pansharpener thermal remotely-sensed imagery to improve its spatial resolution from 70 m to 3 m. Given that pre-existing studies have focused on using GANs to pansharpener satellite imagery in the visible range of the electromagnetic spectrum, this thesis filled a critical gap by investigating the feasibility of using GANs to generate high-resolution thermal imagery. This involved developing a novel training dataset with patch-pairs of co-located thermal (70 m) and RGB imagery (3 m) from the ECOSTRESS and PlanetScope satellite platforms, respectively. The thermal-optical patch-pair dataset was then used to assess whether a pansharpener model (PanColorGAN) trained on RGB and panchromatic imagery could be successfully applied to the thermal-optical patch-pairs to solve the thermal pansharpener problem. In addition, a separate pansharpener model (*pix2pix*) was trained on the thermal-optical patch-pairs to see if it produced higher quality results than the model with pre-trained weights.

Ultimately, the visual and quantitative results indicated that the PanColorGAN framework with pre-trained weights produced higher quality pansharpener thermal images than the *pix2pix* framework trained on the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset. While it is somewhat surprising that a GAN model trained on RGB-panchromatic patch-pairs outperformed a GAN model trained on the thermal-optical patch-pairs for the thermal pansharpener problem, it is important to consider the size of the training dataset. The original PanColorGAN network was trained using 30,000 unique patch-pairs from the Pleiades satellite constellation, whereas the thermal-optical *pix2pix* network was trained only using 11,846 thermal-optical patch-pairs (5,923 unique original patch-pairs and 5,923 augmented patch-pairs). As such, an important step to improving the suitability of the thermal-optical patch-pair dataset is increasing the number of training samples by extending the methods of this thesis to additional cities. Based on the results of the three image quality metrics (RMSE, ERGAS, and SAM), the spatial quality of images pansharpener with both the *pix2pix* and the PanColorGAN architectures was higher than the spectral quality. This suggests that pansharpener successfully recovered many of the spatial details of the high-resolution RGB imagery, but was not fully able to retain the valuable spectral information from the ECOSTRESS LST imagery.

This thesis has highlighted many of the challenges with using GANs to produce synthetic thermal satellite imagery. Additional research on this topic of pansharpener thermal satellite imagery with GANs is certainly needed to produce higher quality image products, perhaps by using Pan-GAN and/or increasing the patch-pair sample training size. Given that the code and thermal-optical patch-pair dataset will be published on Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.6483752), this project can provide a framework and open-source dataset for researchers interested in pursuing work on this topic in the future. Although the quality of the results in this thesis is not yet high enough for climate change or Earth science applications, the method of using GANs for generating synthetic thermal satellite imagery shows promise with further improvements.

Coupled with large-scale urban biodiversity studies and detailed land use/land cover change mapping projects, the fine-scale mapping of temperature will enable researchers to better determine how UHIs affect biodiversity across a range of cities.

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